

BIOLOGIK OBYEKTDAN AJRATIB OLINGAN LOZARTANNI UB-SPEKTROFOTOMETRIYA USULIDA ANIQLASH USLUBINI ISHLAB CHIQISH

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Dolzarbli: Gipertenziya kasalligi bugungi kunda global sog'liqni saqlash muammolaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu kasallik yurak-qon tomir tizimi faoliyatining buzilishi natijasida rivojlanadi va o'z vaqtida davolash choralari ko'rilmasa, yurak ishemik kasalligi, insult, buyrak yetishmovchiligi kabi og'ir oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin [1]. Ushbu kasalliklarni davolashda lozartan dori vositasi ishlatiladi. Lozartan moddasi oq yoki deyarli oq kristall kukun, gigroskopik. Suvda va metanolda oson eriydi, atsetonitrilda kam eriydi. Erish nuqtasi 183,5^o-184,5^oCga teng, molekulyar massasi 461,0 g/mol [2,3]. Og'iz orqali qabul qilinganidan keyin lozartan oshqozon-ichak traktidan tez so'riladi.

Bugungi kunda ushbu moddaning chinligi va miqdorini aniqlash amaldagi me'yoriy hujjatlarga muvofiq, yupqa qatlamli yoki suyuqlik xromatografiyasi usuli bilan, aralashmalarni aniqlash va miqdoriy tahlil esa spektrofotometrik usul bilan amalga oshiriladi. Shunday qilib, ushbu dori shaklining tahlili yetarlicha uzoq va murakkab hisoblanadi, chunki sifat va miqdoriy tahlil alohida o'tkaziladi. Ammo ushbu modda bilan turli darajadagi zaharlanishlar ro'y berganda uni biologik ob'ektlardan ajratib olib identifikatsiya qilish va miqdorini aniqlash uslublari ishlab chiqilmagan.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: biologik ob'ektlardan ajratib olingan lozartanni chinligini UB spektrofotometriya usulida aniqlash uslubini ishlab chiqish.

Materiallar va usullar: Tadqiqot uchun murda ichki a'zolaridan jigar va buyrak olinib 50 mg losartan qo'shilib model biologik ob'ekt tayyorlandi.

Model biologik ob'ektlardan lozartanni V.F.Kramarenko usulida ajratib olindi. Erituvchi sifatida 96% li etil spirti eritmasidan foydalanildi. O'lchovlar Shimadzu UV-1900i (Yaponiya) spektrofotometrda UV-Visible mode spektrometrda 200-400 nm to'lqin uzunligida kvarts kyuvetlarda bajarildi.

Standart eritmani tayyorlash: Lozartanning toza holdagi substansiyasidan 0,005 gr (5 mg) tortib olib uni 5 ml 96% etil spirtida eritildi.

$$C_{stock1} = \frac{5 \text{ mg}}{5 \text{ mL}} = 1 \text{ mg/mL} = 1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Tayyor bo'lgan dastlabgi eritmadan **0,5 ml** olib, uni **5 ml** 96% etil spirtida suyultirildi va 100 µg/mL yetgazildi.

$$C_{stock2} = \frac{1000 \times 0.5}{5} = 100 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Tekshiriluvchi eritmani tayyorlash. Tekshiriluvchi namuna olinib uni 100 ml 96% etil spirtida eritildi va shu eritmadan **1 ml** olib **5 ml** 96% etil spirtida eritildi va 100 µg/ml yetgazildi.

$$C = \frac{500 \times 1}{5} = 100 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Lozartanning substansiyasining 100 µg/ml konsentrsiyadagi eritmasi Shimadzu UV-1900i spektrofotometrda 200-400 nm oralig'ida skanerlash yo'li bilan o'lchandi. Natijada asosiy yutilish maksimumi $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 235 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ to'lqin uzunligida kuzatildi. Yutilish intensivligi (A) ≈ 0.394 bo'lib, bu standart eritmaning o'ziga xos spektral xususiyatini ko'rsatadi.

Rasm №1. Lozartanning UB-spektri

Keyin tekshiriluvchi obyektдан olingan eritmadan 100 µg/ml olib Shimadzu UV-1900i spektrofotometrda 200-400 nm oralig'ida skanerlash yo'li bilan o'lchandi. Natijada asosiy yutilish maksimumi **234-236 nm oralig'ida** kuzatilib, absorbsiya qiymati **0,42-0,44 ga teng bo'ldi**.

Rasm №2. Obyekt tarkibidan ajrtib olingan lozartan UB-spektri

Natijalar: Standart tayyorlangan eritma ($C_{st} = 100 \mu\text{g/mL}$): $A = 0.394$. Obyektdan olingan ajratma eritmasi ($C_{tb} = 100 \mu\text{g/mL}$ ekvivalent): $A = 0.431$ (o'rtacha qiymat sifatida 234–236 nm oralig'idan olindi)

Konsentratsiya hisoblash formulasi:

$$C_{tb} = \frac{A_{tb}}{A_{st}} \times C_{st}$$

$$C_{tb} = \frac{0.431}{0.394} \times 100 = 109.4 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

$$\% = \frac{C_{tb}}{C_{st}} \times 100 = \frac{109.4}{100} \times 100 = 109.4\%$$

Hulosa: Lozartan moddasining tahlil uslubi ishlab chiqildi va uni identifikatsiya qilish va miqdorini aniqlash imkoniyati yaratildi. Lozartan moddasi eritmasi ($100 \mu\text{g/mL}$) uchun $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 235 \pm 1$ nm absorbsiya 0.394 teng bo'ldi. Ichki a'zoldan tayyorlangan ajratma (nominal $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$) uchun aynan shu to'lqin uzunligida λ_{max} da absorbsiya $0,431$ ga teng bo'ldi.

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